

Seed diversity catalogue of the Snap Bean Panel

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Compiled by the Plant Genetic Group of SERIDA

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This working document shows the seed diversity included in the Snap Bean Panel (SBP). Currently, the document contains 300 of the 311 selected lines.

Each picture corresponds to 40 seeds of a homozygous line placed on a 1 cm grid template.

The photos were taken using a Cannon EOS 600D with a 18-135 mm macro zoom lens.

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